

**Supplementary Information:
Platinum, shock-fractured quartz, microspherules, and meltglass widely
distributed in Eastern USA at the Younger Dryas onset (12.8 ka)**

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Supplementary Information Fig. 1 Newtonville sand pit profile showing the location of samples COA-1, the YDB layer, and the pre-YDB COB-1, impact proxies found, and spherule/kg estimates for each sample (see Fig. 1 in the main paper and Supplementary Information Table 1). The original surface was scalped by sandpit mining activities historically and covered later with pit tailings.

Supplementary Information Fig. 2 Shows the context for the sampling. Collecting sediment and OSL samples from eroding bluff at Parsons Island in 2018. The approximate location of the YDB is shown as a red dashed line.

Supplementary Information Fig. 3 OSL dates for Carolina bays and relict dunes in Georgia and South Carolina^{1,2}. Flamingo Bay (38AK469) OSL dates are shown in green. Roman numerals are Marine Isotope Stages.

Newtonville spherules

Microstrat_0-2 cmbd Spherule A (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		O	42.33	66.66	0.06	212598	0.7458928	K
Mag.	: x 2,500	Instrument : 6510(LA)	Al	3.49	3.26	0.04	36630	0.0412464	K
Date	:	Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	12.64	11.34	0.06	148170	0.1867612	K
2023/07/20		Current : ---	Fe	41.54	18.74	0.10	209620	0.9418870	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Total	100.00	100.00				
960		Live time : 23.81 sec.							
		Real Time : 28.46 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule A from Newtonville (0-2 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_0-2 cmbd Spherule B (001)

		Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Volt	: 20.00 kV		O	40.32	68.09	0.06	247175	0.7353332	K
Mag.	: x 1,800	Instrument : 6510 (IA)	Al	1.27	1.27	0.03	13669	0.0130508	K
Date	: 2023/07/20	Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	4.85	4.66	0.04	60924	0.0651147	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Ca	0.33	0.23	0.02	4925	0.0082634	K
		Process Time : T4	Fe	53.23	25.75	0.10	304608	1.1605623	K
		Live time : 28.08 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 33.73 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 5 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule B from Newtonville (0-2 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_0-2 cmbd Spherule C (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 1,300	Instrument : 6510(LA)	C	39.11	53.81	0.02	209718	0.1238555	K
Date	: 2023/07/20	Volt : 20.00 kV	O	36.94	38.15	0.05	337563	0.6770432	K
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Current : ---	Al	0.50	0.31	0.01	22813	0.0146852	K
		Process Time : T4	Si	2.73	1.60	0.01	138766	0.0999893	K
		Live time : 41.65 sec.	Fe	20.73	6.13	0.04	385044	0.9890550	K
		Real Time : 49.51 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 6 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule C from Newtonville (0-2 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_4-6 cmbd Meltglass (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: 20.00 kV	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	56.88	70.20	0.04	699221	0.9735090	K
Date	: x 4,000	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	16.22	11.87	0.03	738841	0.3301452	K
2023/07/13		Current : ---	Si	23.19	16.30	0.04	911113	0.4557289	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	K	2.05	1.03	0.01	72008	0.0557348	K
960		Live time : 60.00 sec.	Fe	1.67	0.59	0.02	24978	0.0445374	K
		Real Time : 73.32 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 7 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for aluminosilicate meltglass from Newtonville (4-6 cmbd), showing major element composition.

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule H (001)

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 3,700	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	30.12	60.07	0.04	335305	2.0763712	K
Date	: 2023/06/23	Volt : 20.00 kV	Fe	69.88	39.93	0.09	710240	5.6327167	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Process Time : T4							
		Live time : 13.49 sec.							
		Real Time : 28.24 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 8 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule H from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule I (001)

Supplementary Information Fig. 9 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an aerodynamically-shaped spherule (spherule I) from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule J (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 1,500	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	32.51	60.55	0.02	1212170	2.2998078	K
Date	: 2023/06/23	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	3.68	4.06	0.02	236469	0.1439895	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Current : ---	Si	2.54	2.70	0.01	187329	0.1276856	K
960		Process Time : T4	Fe	61.27	32.69	0.05	2167743	5.2672472	K
		Live time : 44.03 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 93.97 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 10 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule J from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule K (001)

Parameter	Value	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Volt	: 20.00 kV	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	36.34	66.23	0.03	1232466	3.0104096	K
Mag.	: x 4,300	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	0.95	1.03	0.01	50703	0.0397476	K
Date	: 2023/06/23	Current : ---	Fe	62.71	32.74	0.05	1887287	5.9038639	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Process Time : T4	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Live time : 34.20 sec.							
		Real Time : 84.32 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 11 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule K from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule L (001)

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 1,800 Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Date : 2023/06/23 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 21.66 sec.
 Real Time : 50.54 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	50.86	68.21	0.04	823626	3.1764972	K
Na	1.20	1.12	0.02	31510	0.0647234	K
Al	7.09	5.64	0.02	384605	0.4760602	K
Si	22.54	17.22	0.04	1236545	1.7133144	K
P	0.76	0.53	0.01	30362	0.0580059	K
K	2.35	1.29	0.01	114285	0.2450338	K
Ca	0.86	0.46	0.01	44249	0.0962389	K
Ti	0.41	0.18	0.01	14217	0.0405676	K
Fe	13.93	5.35	0.03	287121	1.4181793	K

Supplementary Information Fig. 12 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for Si-Al-Fe-rich (glassy) spherule L from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule M (001)

		Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Volt	: 20.00 kV		O	34.82	63.31	0.03	945594	2.5358498	K
Mag.	: x 4,300	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	Al	2.27	2.45	0.02	106533	0.0916921	K
Date	: 2023/06/23	Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	2.67	2.77	0.02	145670	0.1403451	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Ca	0.43	0.31	0.01	28751	0.0434818	K
		Process Time : T4	Fe	59.81	31.16	0.05	1542509	5.2977839	K
		Live time : 31.15 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 70.10 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 13 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for Si-Al-Fe-rich (glassy) spherule M from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule N (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		O	37.30	65.87	0.03	760250	2.8301563	K
Mag.	: x 3,000	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	Al	1.87	1.95	0.02	64768	0.0773822	K
Date	:	Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	2.64	2.65	0.02	106744	0.1427596	K
2023/06/23		Current : ---	Ca	0.35	0.24	0.01	16948	0.0355800	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Fe	57.85	29.27	0.06	1097134	5.2307191	K
960		Live time : 22.44 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 52.69 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 14 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule N from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_12-14 cmbd Spherule P (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 2,500	Instrument : 6510 (IA)	O	32.04	61.79	0.04	338900	0.6945672	K
Date	: 2023/06/22	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	1.12	1.28	0.02	18668	0.0122794	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Fe	66.85	36.93	0.09	643435	1.6888657	K
		Process Time : T4	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Live time : 40.76 sec.							
		Real Time : 50.33 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 15 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule P from Newtonville (12-14 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_12-14 cmbd Spherule Q (001)

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	39.63	69.18	0.04	441115	1.0021551	K
Si	1.28	1.27	0.02	26799	0.0218733	K
Fe	59.08	29.55	0.08	577310	1.6797336	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	
Mag.	: x 2,300	Instrument	: 6510 (LA)
Date	: 2023/06/22	Volt	: 20.00 kV
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Current	: ---
		Process Time	: T4
		Live time	: 36.77 sec.
		Real Time	: 47.06 sec.

Supplementary Information Fig. 16 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule Q from Newtonville (12-14 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper). Note multiple small spherules fused to the larger spherule.

Microstrat_12-14 cmbd Spherule R (001)

		Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Volt	: 20.00 kV		O	26.76	55.62	0.02	957491	2.2255297	K
Mag.	: x 11,000	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	Al	0.64	0.78	0.01	36550	0.0272655	K
Date	: 2023/06/22	Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	0.60	0.71	0.01	41048	0.0342767	K
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Current : ---	Fe	72.01	42.88	0.05	2418662	7.1998219	K
		Process Time : T4	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Live time : 35.94 sec.							
		Real Time : 87.45 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 17 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a closeup of spherule R from Newtonville (12-14 cmbd), showing major element composition (see Fig. 7 in main paper).

Microstrat_14-16 cmbd Spherule S (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 1,300	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	46.11	65.84	0.03	1451105	3.9940817	K
Date	: 2023/06/22	Volt : 20.00 kV	Mg	1.03	0.96	0.01	66009	0.0594402	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Current : ---	Al	10.80	9.14	0.02	915796	0.8089938	K
960		Process Time : T4	Si	16.12	13.11	0.03	1356624	1.3414865	K
		Live time : 30.35 sec.	P	0.48	0.35	0.01	32105	0.0437739	K
		Real Time : 91.00 sec.	K	0.96	0.56	0.01	79856	0.1221919	K
			Fe	24.51	10.02	0.03	864237	3.0464838	K
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 18 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for Si-Al-Fe-rich (glassy) spherule from Newtonville (14-16 cmbd), showing major element composition. Note that the multiple holes indicate that the spherule is hollow and has a thin shell.

Supplementary Information Fig. 19 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a broken “teardrop” titanomagnetite spherule from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major elemental composition.

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	20.00 kV		O	35.30	63.66	0.04	425974	1.0469075	K
Mag.	x 700	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	Al	7.85	8.39	0.02	722012	0.5695063	K
Date		Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	13.07	13.42	0.02	1185904	1.0470898	K
2023/07/24		Current : ---	Ti	1.64	0.99	0.01	80694	0.1467312	K
Pixel	640 x 480	Process Time : T4	Fe	0.99	0.51	0.01	30858	0.0971274	K
		Live time : 33.99 sec.	Zr	41.15	13.02	0.07	1936783	2.8210537	L
		Real Time : 74.75 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 20 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a very rare aerodynamically-shaped zircon spherule from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition. The other elements besides Zr, Si, and O result from beam-scattering, in which the EDS beam is reflected and hits nearby grains.

Microstrat_0-2 cmbd Meltglass (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 700	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	36.41	55.53	0.04	373512	0.9943241	K
Date	: 2023/08/18	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	3.91	3.53	0.02	131971	0.1127538	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Si	34.41	29.90	0.05	1228275	1.1747031	K
		Process Time : T4	Fe	25.27	11.04	0.05	335124	1.1425568	K
		Live time : 31.38 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 45.95 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 21 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for agglutinated Si-Al-Fe-rich meltglass with embedded microspherules from Newtonville (microstrat 0-2 cmbd), showing major element composition.

Supplementary Information Fig. 22 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) topographic map of meltglass (melted and bubbled aluminosilicate glass) from Newtonville (microstrat 4-6 cmbd). Raised circular features are the rims of vesicles in the glass.

Supplementary Information Fig. 23 SEM image of potentially shock-fractured zircon from Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd). Insets show locations for Supplementary Information Fig. 24 [a] and 25 [b].

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Shock-fractured Zircon (002)

Supplementary Information Fig. 24 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of potentially shock-fractured zircon (inset 'a' in Supplementary Information Fig. S23) from Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd). Fractures are filled with zircon that appears to be amorphous.

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Shock-fractured Zircon (001)

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	39.08	70.24	0.08	126690	0.7060206	K
Si	14.90	15.25	0.04	399636	0.8001075	K
Zr	46.02	14.50	0.13	609215	2.0121050	L
Total	100.00	100.00				

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	
Mag.	: x 4,000	Instrument	: 6510 (LA)
Date	: 2023/07/24	Volt	: 20.00 kV
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current	: ---
		Process Time	: T4
		Live time	: 14.99 sec.
		Real Time	: 24.35 sec.

Supplementary Information Fig. 25 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of potentially shock-fractured zircon (inset 'b' from Supplementary Information Fig. 23) from Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd). Fractures are filled with zircon that appears to be amorphous.

Microstrat_0-2 cmbd Ulvospinel (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		O	25.54	52.87	0.05	129163	0.1798304	K
Mag.	: x 6,500	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	Al	0.86	1.05	0.02	14514	0.0064855	K
Date	:	Volt : 20.00 kV	Si	1.29	1.52	0.02	25688	0.0128487	K
2023/07/20		Current : ---	Ti	17.03	11.77	0.04	275489	0.2837839	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Fe	55.28	32.78	0.09	499776	0.8911453	K
960		Live time : 60.00 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 68.15 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 26 Scanning electron microscopy images (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy analyses (EDS) show major elemental compositions for ulvöspinel (TiFe_2O_4) from Newtonville (0-2 cmbd). Ulvöspinel has been linked to cosmic airbursts^{3,4}.

Supplementary Information Fig. 27 Newtonville microstrat major elemental abundance data (a-d) from prompt gamma-ray activation analysis (PGAA) (see Supplementary Information Table 7). Some of these elements are sometimes enriched in meteoritic material.

Supplementary Information Fig. 28 Optical image of potentially shock-fractured quartz from the Newtonville microstrat block (10-12 cmbd). Note planar deformation features (PDFs). Grain is ~10 microns in diameter.

Supplementary Information Fig. 29 SEM image of potentially shock-fractured quartz from the Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd). Inset 'a' shows the location of the image in Supplementary Information Fig. 30.

Supplementary Information Fig. 30 Zoomed SEM image of potentially shock-fractured quartz shown in inset 'a' in Supplementary Information Fig. 29 from Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd).

Parsons Island spherules

Parsons Island_40-45 cmbs Spherule A (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 3,000	Instrument : 6510 (IA)	O	40.34	65.56	0.09	98009	0.1924166	K
Date	: 2021/10/07	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	6.12	5.90	0.06	29381	0.0185131	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Si	7.84	7.26	0.07	41146	0.0290212	K
		Process Time : T4	Fe	45.71	21.28	0.15	108774	0.2734960	K
		Live time : 42.55 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Real Time : 44.66 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 31 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule A from Parsons Island (40-45 cmbs) showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_40-45 cmbs Spherule B (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	49.77	69.17	0.08	160690	0.2237248	K
Mag.	: x 5,500	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	11.23	9.25	0.06	97038	0.0433607	K
Date	: 2021/10/07	Current : ---	Si	15.18	12.02	0.07	129096	0.0645722	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Ti	1.13	0.53	0.03	6883	0.0070900	K
960		Live time : 60.00 sec.	Fe	22.68	9.03	0.09	80419	0.1433945	K
		Real Time : 63.25 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 32 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) data for small spherule fused to a much larger spherule B from Parsons Island (40-45 cmbs) showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_40-45 cmbs Spherule C (001)

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 1,400	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	40.71	70.56	0.07	180366	0.2511198	K
Date	: 2021/10/07	Volt : 20.00 kV	Fe	59.29	29.44	0.14	225697	0.4024377	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Current : ---	Total	100.00	100.00				
960		Process Time : T4							
		Live time : 60.00 sec.							
		Real Time : 63.51 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 33 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule C from Parsons Island (40-45 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_45-50 cmbs Spherule D (101)

Supplementary Information Fig. 34 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for Si-Al-Fe-rich spherule D from Parsons Island (45-50 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper). The high carbon content is from the matrix and not the spherule.

Parsons Island_45-50 cmbs Spherule G (101)

	Volt	20.00 kV	WD10mm	SS60	50Pa	x4,300	Sum	0	Oct 17, 2019	
Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition		Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 4,300	Instrument : 6510 (LA)		C	28.44	44.78	0.04	28125	0.0204012	K
Date	: 2019/10/17	Volt : 20.00 kV		O	36.33	42.94	0.09	83264	0.2051197	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---		Al	0.27	0.19	0.02	2231	0.0017637	K
		Process Time : T4		Si	0.66	0.44	0.02	6156	0.0054480	K
		Live time : 33.91 sec.		Ca	0.26	0.12	0.02	2650	0.0036816	K
		Real Time : 35.77 sec.		Fe	34.04	11.53	0.10	128622	0.4057997	K
				Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 35 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) composition for spherule G from Parsons Island (45-50 cmbs), showing the elemental composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_45-50 cmbs Spherule H (101)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 2,200	Instrument : 6510(LA)	C	32.22	50.38	0.03	52377	0.0214725	K
Date	: 2019/10/17	Volt : 20.00 kV	O	31.43	36.90	0.07	108696	0.1513346	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Current : ---	Al	0.48	0.33	0.02	6475	0.0028932	K
	960	Process Time : T4	Si	0.87	0.58	0.02	13480	0.0067424	K
		Live time : 60.00 sec.	Ca	0.23	0.11	0.01	3859	0.0030302	K
		Real Time : 62.77 sec.	Fe	34.78	11.70	0.08	217254	0.3873838	K
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 36 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule H from Parsons Island (45-50 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_45-50cmbs Spherule I (001)

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 7,500 Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Date : 2019/10/17 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 640 x 480 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 46.74 sec.
 Real Time : 48.43 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	43.04	61.77	0.04	46158	0.0242915	K
O	23.72	25.56	0.08	39630	0.0708295	K
Mg	1.29	0.91	0.02	10083	0.0058957	K
Al	0.42	0.27	0.02	4343	0.0024911	K
Si	4.45	2.73	0.04	51553	0.0331019	K
S	0.23	0.12	0.01	2732	0.0021173	K
Ca	2.71	1.17	0.03	30851	0.0310947	K
Ti	0.30	0.11	0.02	2253	0.0029790	K
Fe	23.85	7.36	0.08	101406	0.2321129	K

Supplementary Information Fig. 37 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for Si-Al-Ca-Fe-rich spherule I from Parsons Island (45-50 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper). High carbon content is from the matrix and not the spherule.

Parsons Island_50-55 cmbs Spherule J (001)

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	40.08	68.73	0.04	512735	0.7138683	K
Al	1.39	1.41	0.02	29100	0.0130032	K
Si	2.27	2.22	0.02	55826	0.0279237	K
Fe*	56.26	27.64	0.08	643183	1.1468529	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	
Mag.	: x 3,000	Instrument	: 6510 (LA)
Date	: 2021/07/29	Volt	: 20.00 kV
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current	: ---
		Process Time	: T4
		Live time	: 60.00 sec.
		Real Time	: 71.19 sec.

Supplementary Information Fig. 38 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule J from Parsons Island (50-55 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_50-55 cmbs Spherule K (002)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 2,500	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	51.16	70.25	0.06	382552	0.8752979	K
Date	:	Volt : 20.00 kV	Na	1.11	1.06	0.03	10009	0.0121974	K
2021/07/29	:	Current : ---	Al	3.80	3.09	0.03	73830	0.0542158	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Si	20.55	16.08	0.05	429549	0.3530908	K
960	:	Live time : 36.51 sec.	P	0.77	0.54	0.02	12003	0.0136045	K
	:	Real Time : 43.38 sec.	K	0.44	0.25	0.01	8386	0.0106671	K
	:		Fe	22.17	8.72	0.06	178456	0.5229312	K
	:		Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 39 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule K from Parsons Island (50-55 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper).

Parsons Island_55-60 cmbs Spherule N (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		C	58.48	79.31	0.05	63378	0.0739896	K
Mag.	: x 5,500	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	5.93	6.04	0.05	14738	0.0584329	K
Date	:	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	0.29	0.18	0.01	7833	0.0099675	K
2020/05/19		Current : ---	Si	0.11	0.07	0.01	3315	0.0047214	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Process Time : T4	S	19.10	9.70	0.03	574044	0.9867008	K
960		Live time : 21.07 sec.	Ca	0.12	0.05	0.01	2980	0.0066639	K
		Real Time : 26.40 sec.	Fe	15.97	4.66	0.05	149830	0.7607799	K
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 40 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule N from Parsons Island (55-60 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 10 in main paper). Note severe oxygen depletion (5.93%), indicating cooling under highly reducing conditions (anoxic).

Parsons Island_45-50 cmbs Meltglass (001)

Acquisition Condition			Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Volt	: 20.00 kV	Instrument	C	26.29	38.11	0.03	45116	0.0273609	K
Mag.	: x 550	Volt	O	46.10	50.17	0.07	215949	0.4447636	K
Date	: 2021/09/02	Current	Na	0.37	0.28	0.02	3220	0.0035323	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Process Time	Al	3.97	2.56	0.02	75330	0.0497938	K
		Live time	Si	5.03	3.12	0.03	101990	0.0754648	K
		sec.	K	0.43	0.19	0.01	8362	0.0095742	K
		Real Time	Ti	0.24	0.09	0.01	3185	0.0048534	K
		sec.	Fe	17.58	5.48	0.05	134807	0.3555810	K
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 41 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for aluminosilicate meltglass from Parsons Island (45-50 cmbs), showing major element composition.

Supplementary Information Fig. 42 *Parsons Island Bulk Sedimentary Organic Matter Geochemistry*. Carbon and nitrogen stable isotope analysis for bulk sediments from Parsons Island. The Bayesian modeled age range for the YD onset ($12,835 \pm 35 \text{ cal BP}$ at 95% Confidence Interval) based on Kennett *et al.*⁵ is shown as a light-yellow zone. The stratigraphic position of the Pt and Pt/Pd anomaly, shock-fractured quartz, and meltglass is also shown. See discussion of isotope data below: Supplementary Information, “*Parsons Island Bulk Sedimentary Organic Matter Geochemistry.*”

Supplementary Information Fig. 43 Cumulative granulometry data for Parsons Island samples (40-85 cmbs) below the plowzone showing the stratigraphic position of an AMS date on glass-like carbon (GLC), platinum abundance anomaly, microspherule peak, meltglass, and single-grain OSL date at 65 cmbs.

Flamingo Bay (38AK469)

Flamingo Bay_52.5-55 cmbs Spherule A (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		C	23.33	37.10	0.21	623	0.0003008	K
Mag.	: x 1,500	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	43.06	51.41	0.55	3036	0.0049783	K
Date	: 2022/03/24	Volt : 20.00 kV	Fe	33.60	11.49	0.64	3370	0.0070774	K
Pixel	: 1280 x	Current : ---	Total	100.00	100.00				
960		Process Time : T4							
		Live time : 50.94 sec.							
		Real Time : 51.05 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 44 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for spherule A from Flamingo Bay (52.5-55 cmbs), showing major element composition (see Fig. 12 in main paper).

Flamingo Bay_52.5-55 cmbs Spherule B (001)

Supplementary Information Fig. 45 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) composition for spherule B from Flamingo Bay (52.5-55 cmbs), showing major element (see Fig. 12 in main paper).

High-temperature melted minerals:

Newtonville

Supplementary Information Fig. 46 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a mineralized carbon spherule from Newtonville (COA-1) embedded with melted blebs (lighter-colored) that are enriched in PGEs, including osmium (1.26 wt%; melting point = 3053° C), iridium (1.16 wt%; melting point = 2466° C), and platinum (2.05 wt%; melting point = 1768° C). Note oxygen depletion, consistent with quenching under reducing conditions.

Quantitative Results for Probe 1
Analysis: Bulk Method: Standards
Acquired 30-Oct-2009, 20.0 KeV @10 eV/channel

Element	Weight %	Std. Dev.	MDL	Atomic %	k-Ratio	Intensities	FWHM (eV)	ROI (net)
C ?	0.05	0.02	0.74	0.22	0.0031	35.6	65.9	-31.85
N ?	0.03	0.02	0.76	0.12	0.0012	27.1	67.6	
O ?	0.54	0.21	0.60	1.83	0.0092	267.0	69.8	294.55
Na ?	0.01	0.01	20.91	0.03	0.0000	1.8	78.9	3.01
Al ?	0.12	0.06	4.95	0.24	0.0004	29.1	84.8	79.92
Si ?	0.19	0.09	2.45	0.37	0.0009	67.7	88.3	190.03
K ?	0.18	0.08	1.31	0.25	0.0017	98.2	107.7	299.56
Ca ?	0.30	0.13	0.98	0.41	0.0031	167.5	111.7	357.91
Ti B	3.62	0.96	0.31	4.13	0.0383	1598.7	119.9	1834.91
Cr ?	0.05	0.03	2.14	0.05	0.0006	23.1	128.0	371.41
Fe B	91.88	2.44	0.10	89.84	0.9122	23534.3	137.3	23503.19
Co B	1.47	0.53	0.83	1.37	0.0144	315.0	141.9	
Ni ?	0.40	0.19	2.01	0.38	0.0036	62.1	146.1	191.64
Cu ?	0.31	0.15	2.69	0.26	0.0027	40.9	150.9	172.14
Zn ?	0.53	0.24	2.24	0.44	0.0047	60.0	155.5	183.52
Th ?	0.08	0.05	3.39	0.02	0.0007	28.5	103.8	186.82
U ?	0.23	0.11	1.94	0.05	0.0020	80.2	105.4	235.33
Total	100.00							

? These elements are statistically insignificant.
B. Element by standardless analysis.

Supplementary Information Fig. 47 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a melted Fe-rich grain from Newtonville (COA-1) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO with 91.88 wt% Fe; melting point = 1538° C), suggesting that it formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

001

	volt	: 20.00 kv	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Act	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 7,500		Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	4.17	12.54	0.02	14785	0.0271752	K
Date	: 2023/07/13		Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	1.97	3.51	0.03	12339	0.0012184	K
			Current : ---	Si	3.61	6.18	0.04	26631	0.0175850	K
Pixel	: 640 x 480		Process Time : T4	Fe	90.25	77.76	0.17	342177	0.8054557	K
			Live time : 45.45 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
			Real Time : 48.25 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 48 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a small, melted Fe-rich spherule from Newtonville (microstrat) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO; melting point = 1538° C), suggesting that it formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

001

	Volt	Mag.	Date	Pixel	Acquisition Condition	Instrument	Current	Process Time	Live time	Real Time	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV	: x 8,000	: 2023/07/20	: 640 x 480		: 6510(LA)	: ---	: T4	: 44.28	: 46.45	O	8.30	21.09	0.64	21223	0.0400378	K
											Al	12.00	18.07	0.67	62029	0.0375573	K
											Si	3.97	5.74	0.05	21740	0.0147346	K
											Fe	75.73	55.10	0.18	217076	0.5244810	K
											Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 49 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a melted Fe-rich spherule from Newtonville (microstrat) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO; melting point = 1538°C), suggesting that they formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

001

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 1,300	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	14.83	37.80	0.03	125965	0.4190632	K
Date	: 2023/08/18	Volt : 20.00 kV	Fe	85.17	62.20	0.11	710111	3.0255487	K
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Current : ---	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Process Time : 04							
		Live time : 25.11 sec.							
		Real Time : 33.40 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 50 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for melted Fe-rich material attached to an Fe-rich microspherule from Newtonville (microstrat) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO; melting point = 1538° C), suggesting that they formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

001

		Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Volt	: 20.00 kV		O	7.46	21.95	0.03	35779	0.1255822	K
Mag.	: x 3,000	Instrument : 6510(LA)	Fe	92.54	78.05	0.15	448582	2.0164614	K
Date	: 2023/08/18	Volt : 20.00 kV	Total	100.00	100.00				
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Current : ---							
		Process Time : T4							
		Live Line : 23.80 sec.							
		Real Time : 27.98 sec.							

Supplementary Information Fig. 51 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a broken Fe-rich spherule from Newtonville (microstrat) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO; melting point = 1538° C), suggesting that they formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

002

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	6.20	18.75	0.03	21552	0.1092476	K
Fe	93.80	81.25	0.18	330696	2.1468215	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition	
Mag.	: x 3,000	Instrument	: 6510(LA)
Date	: 2023/08/18	Volt	: 20.00 kV
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Current	: ---
		Process Time	: T4
		Live Time	: 16.48 sec.
		Real Time	: 19.25 sec.

Supplementary Information Fig. 52 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an Fe-rich spherule from Newtonville (microstrat) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO; melting point = 1538° C), suggesting that they formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

Quantitative Results for Probe 1
Analysis: Bulk Method: Standardless
Acquired 29-Oct-2009, 20.0 KeV @10 eV/channel

Element	Weight %	Std. Dev.	MDL	Atomic %	k-Ratio	Intensities	Probability	FWHM (eV)	ROI (net)
C ?	0.77	0.38	1.92	2.96	0.0241	34.8	0.00	65.5	54.44
O	5.58	1.48	1.84	16.02	0.0396	144.7	0.93	69.8	161.93
Mg ?	0.23	0.17	18.00	0.43	0.0006	5.7	0.00	81.3	
Al ?	0.86	0.44	7.09	1.46	0.0031	28.6	0.00	84.7	66.28
Si ?	1.70	0.70	3.21	2.78	0.0085	80.7	0.00	88.2	100.96
S ?	0.03	0.03	16.83	0.04	0.0002	1.9	0.00	95.6	-2.60
K ?	0.01	0.02	19.07	0.02	0.0001	1.0	0.00	107.5	10.45
Ca ?	0.00	0.01	3.87	0.00	0.0000	0.2	0.00	112.1	30.47
Ti	11.45	1.01	0.74	10.98	0.1183	624.9	0.98	119.9	704.05
Mn ?	0.03	0.04	20.19	0.03	0.0003	1.1	0.00	133.0	31.08
Fe	79.34	3.17	0.47	65.28	0.7673	2505.6	0.95	137.3	2369.90
Total	100.00								

? These elements are statistically insignificant.

Supplementary Information Fig. 53 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an Fe-rich broken spherule from Newtonville (COA-1) that is highly depleted in oxygen (FeO; melting point = 1538°C), suggesting that they formed under highly reducing conditions that are extremely rare on the Earth but common in impact-related material.

Supplementary Information Fig. 54 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a broken, aerodynamically-shaped titanomagnetite spherule from Newtonville (microstrat).

001

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	26.03	54.18	0.05	129163	0.1798304	K
Ti	17.38	12.08	0.04	275488	0.2837839	K
Fe	56.59	33.74	0.09	499776	0.8911453	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Volt	: 20.00 kV	Acquisition Condition
Mag.	: x 6,500	Instrument : 6510(LA)
Date	: 2023/07/20	Volt : 20.00 kV
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---
		Process Time : T4
		Live time : 60.00 sec.
		Real Time : 68.15 sec.

Supplementary Information Fig. 55 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy analyses (EDS) show major elemental compositions for ulvöspinel particle (TiFe_2O_4) from Newtonville (0-2 cmbd). Ulvöspinel has been linked to cosmic airbursts^{3,4}.

Quantitative Results for Probe 1
Analysis: Bulk Method: Standardless
Acquired 29-Oct-2009, 20.0 KeV @10 eV/channel

Element	Weight %	Std. Dev.	MDL	Atomic %	k-Ratio	Intensities	Probability	FWHM (eV)	ROI (net)
C ?	0.77	0.38	1.92	2.96	0.0241	34.8	0.00	65.5	54.44
O	5.58	1.48	1.84	16.02	0.0396	144.7	0.93	69.8	161.93
Mg ?	0.23	0.17	18.00	0.43	0.0006	5.7	0.00	81.3	
Al ?	0.86	0.44	7.09	1.46	0.0031	28.6	0.00	84.7	66.28
Si ?	1.70	0.70	3.21	2.78	0.0085	80.7	0.00	88.2	100.96
S ?	0.03	0.03	16.83	0.04	0.0002	1.9	0.00	95.6	-2.60
K ?	0.01	0.02	19.07	0.02	0.0001	1.0	0.00	107.5	10.45
Ca ?	0.00	0.01	3.87	0.00	0.0000	0.2	0.00	112.1	30.47
Ti	11.45	1.01	0.74	10.98	0.1183	624.9	0.98	119.9	704.05
Mn ?	0.03	0.04	20.19	0.03	0.0003	1.1	0.00	133.0	31.08
Fe	79.34	3.17	0.47	65.28	0.7673	2505.6	0.95	137.3	2369.90
Total	100.00								

? These elements are statistically insignificant.

Supplementary Information Fig. 56 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an Fe-rich broken spherule from Newtonville (COA-1) showing major elemental compositions for ulvöspinel (TiFe_2O_4)^{3,4}.

Microstrat_11-13 cmbd Spherule (001)

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
Mag.	: x 700	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	35.30	63.66	0.04	425974	1.0469075	K
Date	:	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	7.85	8.39	0.02	722012	0.5695063	K
2023/07/24		Current : ---	Si	13.07	13.42	0.02	1185904	1.0470898	K
Pixel	: 640 x 480	Process Time : T4	Ti	1.64	0.99	0.01	80694	0.1467312	K
		Live time : 33.99 sec.	Fe	0.99	0.51	0.01	30858	0.0971274	K
		Real Time : 74.75 sec.	Zr	41.15	13.02	0.07	1936783	2.8210537	L
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 57 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for aerodynamically-shaped zircon spherule from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd), showing major element composition.

010

	Volt	Mag.	Date	Pixel	Acquisition Condition	Instrument	Vol_t	Current	Process Time	Live time	Real Time	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV	: x 5,500	: 2023/07/24	: 1280 x 960		: 6510(LA)	: 20.00 kV	: ---	: 74	: 39.21 sec.	: 49.09 sec.	O	38.67	67.74	0.10	84050	0.1837549	K
												Si	19.43	19.39	0.06	341955	0.2695824	K
												Zr	41.90	12.87	0.16	346652	0.4491569	L
												Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 58 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) showing a closeup image of the melted surface and the elemental composition for an aerodynamically-shaped zircon spherule (see Supplementary Information Fig. 57) from Newtonville (11-13 cmbd).

Supplementary Information Fig. 59 SEM image of shock-fractured zircon candidate from Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd).

003

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	36.26	67.65	0.08	110417	0.5793865	K
Si	15.63	16.61	0.05	410131	0.7731528	K
Zr	48.11	15.74	0.13	617692	1.9209241	L
Total	100.00	100.00				

Acquisition Condition	
Instrument	: 6510(LA)
Volt	: 20.00 kV
Current	: ---
Process Time	: T4
Live time	: 15.92 sec.
Real Time	: 25.08 sec.

Volt	: 20.00 kV
Mag.	: x 4,000
Date	: 2023/07/24
Pixel	: 1280 x 960

Supplementary Information Fig. 60 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of shock-fractured zircon candidate from Newtonville microstrat block (11-13 cmbd). Fractures are filled with zircon that appears to be amorphous.

Supplementary Information Fig. 61 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of shock-fractured zircon candidate from Newtonville microstrat (11-13 cmbd). Fractures are filled with zircon that appears to be amorphous.

Supplementary Information Fig. 62 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) of shock-fractured zircon candidate from Newtonville microstrat (11-13 cmbd). Fractures are filled with zircon that appears to be amorphous.

Parsons Island

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 3,000 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/10/07 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : 04
 Live Line : 42.55
 sec.
 Real Time : 44.66
 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	40.35	65.98	0.09	97391	0.1912032	K
Al	5.91	5.73	0.06	29397	0.0185229	K
Si	7.55	7.03	0.07	41107	0.0289935	K
Cr*	0.30	0.15	0.03	1096	0.0020554	K
Fe	44.37	20.78	0.15	108767	0.2734776	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.54	0.15	0.08	1640	0.0021832	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh*	0.15	0.04	0.06	543	0.0007054	L
Pd*	0.23	0.06	0.06	714	0.0010874	L
Os*	0.01	0.00	0.19	14	0.0000211	M
Ir*	0.33	0.04	0.12	780	0.0011214	M
Pt*	0.26	0.04	0.13	644	0.0009391	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 63 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 1,500 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/10/07 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 56.89 sec.
 Real Time : 60.00 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	35.68	66.89	0.07	130264	0.1912787	K
Cr*	0.07	0.04	0.03	394	0.0005526	K
Fe	60.16	32.32	0.14	210775	0.3963769	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.06	0.03	0.05	132	0.0003490	K
Mo*	0.31	0.10	0.06	1380	0.0013737	L
Ru*	0.06	0.02	0.05	284	0.0002687	L
Rh*	0.05	0.01	0.05	259	0.0002516	L
Pd*	0.19	0.05	0.05	862	0.0009826	L
Os*	2.07	0.33	0.15	6807	0.0074604	M
Ir*	0.49	0.08	0.10	1742	0.0018746	M
Pt*	0.86	0.13	0.11	3041	0.0033149	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 64 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 2,200 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/10/07 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 640 x 480 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 41.08 sec.
 Real Time : 43.44 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	30.87	42.31	0.04	32687	0.0195719	K
O	44.40	45.68	0.09	114053	0.2319278	K
Al	5.58	3.41	0.03	84620	0.0552262	K
Si	9.87	5.78	0.04	150747	0.1101295	K
K	1.25	0.53	0.02	16610	0.0187770	K
Ti	1.60	0.55	0.02	14610	0.0219810	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	5.66	1.67	0.04	30050	0.0782601	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.14	0.02	0.03	1073	0.0014798	L
Ru*	0.07	0.01	0.02	625	0.0008188	L
Rh*	0.03	0.01	0.02	291	0.0003914	L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	0.33	0.03	0.04	2019	0.0030087	M
Pt*	0.18	0.02	0.04	1142	0.0017243	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 65 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 5,500 Instrument : 6510 (LA)
 Date : 2021/10/07 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 96C Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00 sec.
 Real Time : 63.25 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	49.38	69.49	0.08	159763	0.2224339	K
Al	10.88	9.08	0.06	97026	0.0433551	K
Si	14.63	11.73	0.07	128839	0.0644441	K
Ti	1.11	0.52	0.03	6883	0.0070900	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	21.97	8.86	0.09	80407	0.1433735	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.17	0.06	0.04	431	0.0010803	K
Mo*	0.29	0.07	0.06	1298	0.0012253	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.02	0.00	0.04	97	0.0001046	L
Os*	0.53	0.06	0.16	1731	0.0017987	M
Ir*	0.62	0.07	0.10	2160	0.0022039	M
Pt*	0.40	0.05	0.11	1434	0.0014827	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 66 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) showing an embedded spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

002

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 2,500 Instrument : 6510(TA)
 Date : 2021/07/29 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : 14
 Live time : 36.51
 sec. Real Time : 43.38
 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	50.87	70.44	0.06	379549	0.8684251	K
Na	1.09	1.05	0.02	10003	0.0121899	K
Al	3.71	3.05	0.03	73752	0.0541588	K
Si	20.07	15.83	0.05	429330	0.3529109	K
P	0.77	0.55	0.02	12392	0.0140456	K
K	0.44	0.25	0.01	8386	0.0106671	K
Cr*	0.05	0.02	0.02	592	0.0012946	K
Fe	21.71	8.61	0.06	178517	0.5231079	K
Co*	0.03	0.01	0.03	188	0.0006495	K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.41	0.10	0.04	4149	0.0064376	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os*	0.44	0.05	0.11	3215	0.0054902	M
Ir	nd	nd				M
Pt*	0.42	0.05	0.07	3414	0.0057990	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 68 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 2,300 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/07/29 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00
 sec. Real Time : 70.43
 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	34.71	64.13	0.04	420279	0.5851447	K
Al	0.84	0.92	0.02	17502	0.0078206	K
Si	2.33	2.46	0.02	57694	0.0288580	K
Ca	0.22	0.16	0.01	6584	0.0051698	K
Cr	0.02	0.01	0.01	424	0.0005638	K
Fe	60.46	32.00	0.08	701505	1.2508464	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	0.08	0.04	0.02	615	0.0015430	K
Mo	0.45	0.14	0.03	6630	0.0062592	L
Ru	0.02	0.01	0.03	388	0.0003481	L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir	0.72	0.11	0.05	8247	0.0084127	M
Pt	0.14	0.02	0.05	1611	0.0016653	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 69 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kv Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 2,700 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : Volt : 20.00 kv
 2021/07/29 Current : ---
 Pixel : 1280 x Process Time : 14
 960 Live time : 60.00
 sec. Real Time : 70.31
 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	38.94	67.04	0.04	449847	0.6263111	K
Al	1.42	1.45	0.02	31468	0.0140614	K
Si	5.20	5.10	0.03	134075	0.0670628	K
Ca	0.28	0.19	0.01	8209	0.0064456	K
Ti	0.56	0.32	0.01	11287	0.0116263	K
Cr*	0.01	0.00	0.01	118	0.0001574	K
Fe	51.78	25.53	0.07	602846	1.0749290	K
Co*	0.01	0.00	0.03	91	0.0001922	K
Ni*	0.04	0.02	0.02	294	0.0007362	K
Mo*	0.55	0.16	0.03	8131	0.0076764	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.06	0.02	0.03	966	0.0010433	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	1.01	0.14	0.05	11570	0.0118021	M
Pt*	0.15	0.02	0.05	1781	0.0018406	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 70 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a spherule from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

004

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 110 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/09/02 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 43.64
 sec.
 Real Time : 46.66
 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	47.97	66.97	0.09	119769	0.2292639	K
Al	10.73	8.88	0.05	109009	0.0669706	K
Si	16.40	13.04	0.07	162234	0.1115686	K
Ca	8.74	4.87	0.05	87259	0.0941959	K
Ti	0.23	0.11	0.02	1502	0.0021271	K
Cr*	0.04	0.02	0.02	191	0.0003488	K
Fe	14.92	5.97	0.07	58211	0.1427074	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.12	0.05	0.03	341	0.0011762	K
Mo*	0.03	0.01	0.05	136	0.0001769	L
Ru*	0.03	0.01	0.04	177	0.0002178	L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os*	0.09	0.01	0.14	304	0.0004350	M
Ir*	0.55	0.06	0.08	2097	0.0029409	M
Pt*	0.15	0.02	0.09	595	0.0008449	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 71 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a grain from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 130 Instrument : 6510 (TA)
 Date : 2021/09/02 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 640 x 480 Current : ---
 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 28.83 sec.
 Real Time : 31.03 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	46.05	68.53	0.09	118108	0.3422206	K
Al	5.78	5.10	0.05	35908	0.0333926	K
Si	15.29	12.97	0.38	101364	0.1055175	K
Cr	nd	nd				K
Fe	30.75	13.11	0.12	84352	0.3130212	K
Co*	0.01	0.00	0.35	15	0.0000642	K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.08	0.02	0.06	279	0.0005478	L
Ru*	0.09	0.02	0.05	359	0.0006706	L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os*	0.12	0.01	0.18	281	0.0006081	M
Ir*	1.98	0.20	0.11	4136	0.0087810	M
Pt*	0.25	0.03	0.12	666	0.0014338	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 72 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a grain from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 700 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/09/02 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Process Time : T4
 960 Live time sec. : 36.67
 Real Time sec. : 40.10

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	36.30	65.63	0.07	121289	0.2763034	K
Al	0.85	0.92	0.03	6969	0.0050949	K
Si	0.86	0.88	0.03	8207	0.0067170	K
Ti	8.25	4.98	0.04	64000	0.1078707	K
Cr*	0.08	0.04	0.02	496	0.0010786	K
Fe	52.80	27.35	0.12	230658	0.6729504	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.39	0.12	0.05	2214	0.0034206	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.06	0.02	0.04	333	0.0005890	L
Os*	0.12	0.02	0.12	507	0.0008628	M
Ir*	0.17	0.03	0.08	771	0.0012868	M
Pt*	0.12	0.02	0.09	560	0.0009466	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 73 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM image) and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) showing a grain from Parsons Island enriched in PGEs.

001

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	30.17	62.97	0.02	99100	0.0406273	K
O	3.36	5.26	0.02	29816	0.0415126	K
Na	0.43	0.47	0.02	5750	0.0042636	K
Al	1.58	1.47	0.01	50108	0.0223905	K
Si	1.14	1.02	0.01	42011	0.0210136	K
P	0.17	0.14	0.01	5864	0.0040447	K
S	0.11	0.09	0.01	4673	0.0028208	K
Cr	12.51	6.03	0.03	306160	0.4072510	K
Fe	45.54	20.45	0.06	744110	1.3268160	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	4.84	2.07	0.03	53562	0.1343111	K
Mo*	0.07	0.02	0.04	1463	0.0013817	L
Ru*	0.03	0.01	0.02	858	0.0007694	L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir	nd	nd				M
Pt*	0.05	0.01	0.03	799	0.0008261	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 74 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a chromferite ($\text{Fe}_{1.5}\text{Cr}_{0.2}$) grain from Parsons Island with a melting point of $\sim 1900^\circ\text{C}$. The EDS shows carbon, but it is only present in the SEM substrate and not in the chromferite flake.

Flamingo Bay spherules

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 250 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2022/01/13 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 60.00 sec.
 Real Time : 65.91 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	78.45	83.26	0.02	969196	0.3973331	K
O	20.59	16.41	0.04	97282	0.1354430	K
Al	0.38	0.18	0.01	23554	0.0105249	K
Si	0.20	0.09	0.01	13109	0.0065569	K
Cr*	0.01	0.00	0.01	175	0.0002324	K
Fe*	0.19	0.04	0.01	3536	0.0063053	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.02	0.00	0.01	804	0.0007589	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.03	0.00	0.01	857	0.0009258	L
Os	nd	nd				M
Ir*	0.08	0.01	0.02	2277	0.0023226	M
Pt*	0.05	0.00	0.02	1281	0.0013240	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Information Fig. 75 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a carbon spherule from Flamingo Bay embedded with melted PGE-rich blebs. The Pd abundance was 300 ppm (melting point = 2334° C), Ir averaged 800 ppm (melting point = 2466° C), and Pt was 500 ppm (melting point = 1768° C). Cr averaged 100 ppm (melting point = 1907° C).

Supplementary Information Fig. 76 Fig. 2 from Wolbach et al.⁶ shows a strong correlation of Pt anomaly from GISP2 compared to GISP2 cumulative concentrations of various elements in sea salt and continental dust as proxies for windiness. Stacked gray lines represent the concentrations of Cl, Ca, Na, Mg, and K. The dotted black line is a lowess curve (50-y half window) that shows data trends. Pt is shown on a semi-log Y-axis for greater clarity. Results indicate that a peak in impact-related Pt (asterisk) coincides precisely with a peak at the onset of increased dust due to climate-related windiness (plus sign), rising to an anomalous dust peak higher than ~99.7% of values in the previous 100,000 y. Data are from Mayewski et al.⁷ and Petaev et al.⁸

Supplementary Information Fig. 77 Graph modified from Glass and Simonson⁹ showing the log number of microtektites/spherules per square centimeter versus log distance from the source crater in kilometers (km). Typical YDB sites average ~1 or less microspherule per cm^2 .

Supplementary Information Fig. 78 Comparison of novel YDB impact spherule layer to the North American strewn field. The YDB spherule layer (A) comprises multiple distal ejecta fields from local or regional airbursts, some overlapping. Here is a small selection of the ~50 YDB sites: 1. Murray Springs, Arizona¹⁰; 2. Blackville, South Carolina¹¹ & Flamingo Bay, South Carolina (this study); 3. Newtonville, New Jersey & Parsons Island, Maryland (this study); 4. Melrose, Pennsylvania¹¹; 5. Lake Cuitzeo, Mexico¹²; 6. Mucunuque, Venezuela^{13,14}; 7. Pica, Chile¹⁵; 8. Pilauco, Chile^{16,17}. The North American strewn field (B) comprises a single distal ejecta field from a large crater-forming impact, perhaps the Chesapeake Bay impact¹⁸. Red areas are proximal ejecta radii, purple areas are distal ejecta fields, and yellow circle is the Chesapeake Bay impact crater.

Supplementary Information Tables

Supplementary Information Table 1. Spherules/kilogram, Pt and Pt/Pd data, meltglass, and shock-fractured quartz data for Newtonville.

Sample Depth	Depth	Spherules/Kg	Pt (ppb)	Pd	Pt/Pd	Meltglass	Shock Fractured Quartz
Newtonville/Micro	0 to 2 cmbd	42	0.7	0.3	2.3	Present	nd
Newtonville/Micro	2 to 4 cmbd	nd	0.7	0.3	2.3	nd	nd
Newtonville/Micro	4 to 6 cmbd	43	0.5	0.3	1.7	Present	nd
Newtonville/Micro	6 to 8 cmbd	nd	0.6	0.5	1.2	nd	nd
Newtonville/Micro	8 to 10 cmbd	nd	1.4	0.9	1.6	nd	nd
Newtonville/Micro	10 to 12 cmbd	1985	0.9	0.4	2.3	Present	0 grains
Newtonville/Micro	11 to 13 cmbd	4483	1.5	0.7	2.1	Present	6 grains
Newtonville/Micro	12 to 14 cmbd	243	1.4	0.4	3.5	nd	nd
Newtonville/Micro	14 to 16 cmbd	13	0.7	0.3	2.3	nd	nd
Newtonville/Micro	16 to 18 cmbd	0	0.7	0.3	2.3	nd	nd
Newtonville/COA-1	19-33 cmbd	10000	nd	nd	nd	Present	8 grains
Newtonville/COB-1	20-33 cmbd	2000	nd	nd	nd	Absent	0 grains

nd = no data; cmbs=centimeters below datum; cmbd=centimeters below datum

Supplementary Information Table 2. Spherules/kilogram, Pt and Pt/Pd data, meltglass, and shock-fractured quartz data for Parsons Island.

Sample Depth	Depth	Spherules/Kg	Pt (ppb)	Pd	Pt/Pd	Meltglass	Shock Fractured Quartz
Parsons Island	30 to 35 cmbs	0	nd	nd	nd	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	35 to 40 cmbs	nd	nd	nd	nd	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	40 to 45 cmbs	100	1.1	2.6	0.42	Absent	0 grains
Parsons Island	45 to 50 cmbs	500	2.2	2.1	1.05	Present	22 grains
Parsons Island	50 to 55 cmbs	25	0.9	1.6	0.56	Absent	0 grains
Parsons Island	55 to 60 cmbs	15	1	2.1	0.48	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	60 to 65 cmbs	0	0.7	1.1	0.64	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	65 to 70 cmbs	nd	0.8	1.4	0.57	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	70 to 75 cmbs	nd	0.7	1	0.70	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	75 to 80 cmbs	nd	0.7	1.1	0.64	Absent	nd
Parsons Island	80 to 85 cmbs	nd	1.2	1.6	0.75	Absent	nd

nd = no data

Supplementary Information Table 3. Spherules/kilogram, Pt and Pt/Pd data, meltglass, and shock-fractured quartz data for Flamingo Bay.

Sample Depth	Depth	Spherules/Kg	Pt (ppb)	Pd	Pt/Pd	Meltglass	Shock Fractured Quartz
Flamingo Bay	30-32.5 cmbs	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	0 grains
Flamingo Bay	40-42.5 cmbs	0	1.4	0.9	1.6	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	42.5-45 cmbs	nd	0.3	0.5	0.6	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	45-47.5 cmbs	1	0.2	0.5	0.4	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	47.5-50 cmbs	7	0.6	0.6	1.0	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	50-52.5 cmbs	0	0.5	0.6	0.8	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	50-52.5 (dup)	0	0.4	1	0.4	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	52.5-55 cmbs	13	65.6	133	0.5	Absent	5 grains
Flamingo Bay	52.5-55 (dup)	13	6.4	1.6	4.0	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	55-57.5 cmbs	0	0.3	0.5	0.6	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	55-57.5 (dup)	0	0.5	0.5	1.0	Absent	nd
Flamingo Bay	57.5-60 cmbs	0	0.4	0.4	1.0	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	60-62.5 cmbs	nd	0.6	1.1	0.5	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	62.5-65 cmbs	nd	0.4	0.3	1.3	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	65-67.5 cmbs	nd	0.3	0.4	0.8	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	67.5-70 cmbs	nd	0.6	0.6	1.0	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	70-72.5 cmbs	nd	0.3	0.6	0.5	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	72.5-75 cmbs	nd	0.2	0.5	0.4	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	75-77.5 cmbs	nd	0.5	1.2	0.4	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	77.5-80 cmbs	nd	0.5	0.1	5.0	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	77.5-80 (dup)	nd	<0.1	0.1	1.0	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	80-82.5 cmbs	nd	0.2	0.1	2.0	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	82.5-85 cmbs	nd	0.2	0.1	2.0	nd	nd
Flamingo Bay	85-87.5cmbs	nd	0.1	0.1	1.0	nd	0 grains
Flamingo Bay	87.5-90 cmbs	nd	0.2	0.1	2.0	nd	nd

nd = no data

Supplementary Information Table 4. Newtonville results from Bayesian analysis.

AgeDepth_Model	Unmodelled (BP)						Modelled (BP) Amodel 107.1, Aoverall 106.8						Indices	
	μ	σ	from 68.3	to 68.3	from 95.4	to 95.4	μ	σ	from 68.3	to 68.3	from 95.4	to 95.4	A	C
Boundary							11976	208	12309	11815	12333	11728		1.2
R_Date UGA-65781	853	37	916	802	923	793	853	37	916	803	923	793		99.9
R_Date UGA-65780	853	37	916	802	923	793	853	37	916	803	923	793		99.9
R_Date UCI-250410	11852	53	11932	11815	11939	11751	11976	208	12309	11815	12333	11728	100.2	1.2
R_Date D-AMS 043966	12783	29	12822	12745	12833	12738	12629	220	12815	12267	12841	...	102.2	0.7
C_Date Pt Anomaly	12786	50	12837	12734	12886	12686	12633	222	12818	12267	12854	...	113.2	0.7
C_Date UIC 1295	16746	1700	18447	15045	20146	13346	17164	1734	18927	...	20407	...	100	55.2
Boundary							17164	1734	18927	...	20407	...		55.2
P_Sequence Newtonville														
U(0,3)	1.52	0.87	0.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	1.60	1.03	3.60E-17	3	3.60E-17	3	100	9.6
Exp(1,-10,0.5)	-0.55	1.00	-0.66	0.45	-2.69	0.45	-0.44	0.86						40.1
Outlier_Model General							-88	326	-525	26	-612	...		0.1

Supplementary Information Table 5. Parsons Island results from Bayesian analysis.

AgeDepth_Model	Unmodelled (BP)						Modelled (BP) Amodel=140.1; Aoverall=137.4						Indices	
	μ	σ	from 68.3	to 68.3	from 95.4	to 95.4	μ	σ	from 68.3	to 68.3	from 95.4	to 95.4	A	C
Boundary							12785	40	12820	12735	12880	12720		98.5
DAMS 043965 R_Date	12730	15	12750	12720	12760	12700	12785	40	12820	12735	12880	12720	97.4	98.5
Pt anomaly C_Date	12785	50	12840	12730	12890	12685	12825	35	12845	12775	12905	12775	132.3	98.4
UW3800 C_Date	17330	2270	19605	15055	21870	12785	15685	1540	17240	13875	18390	12810	95.5	99.7
UW3801 C_Date	19230	1560	20795	17665	22350	16105	19035	1205	20280	17845	21390	16600	111.1	99.7
UW3802 C_Date	21130	1780	22915	19345	24690	17565	21315	1210	22510	20045	23715	18895	116.7	99.8
UW3803 C_Date	24130	1640	25775	22485	27410	20845	23740	1240	24955	22440	26250	21285	109.9	99.7
UW3804 C_Date	24530	2400	26935	22125	29330	19725	25170	1570	26555	23330	28300	22155	116.8	98.4
Boundary							25170	1570	26555	23330	28300	22155		98.4
Parsons Island P_Sequence														
U(0,4)	3.99E-17	4	3.99E-17	4	2	1.143	0.108	1.156	5.38E-17	1.172	0.630	0.351	100	94.4
Exp(1,10,10)	8.660	9.900	6.720	9.900	8.897	0.998					8.889	0.995		100
General Outlier_Model							5	70	5	130	50	35		98.6

Supplementary Information Table 6. Flamingo Bay results from Bayesian analysis.

AgeDepth_Model	Unmodelled (BP)						Modelled (BP) Amodel 105, Aoverall 105.2						Indices	
	μ	σ	from 68.3	to 68.3	from 95.4	to 95.4	μ	σ	from 68.3	to 68.3	from 95.4	to 95.4	A	C
Boundary							1172	366	1533	839	1914	441		99.4
C_Date Woodland point	1176	325	1502	850	1826	526	1172	366	1533	839	1914	441	99.1	99.4
C_Date Savannah River point	4276	575	4852	3700	5426	3126	4143	553	4708	3609	5247	3027	103.4	99.3
C_Date Middle Archaic point	7401	1500	8902	5900	10401	4401	7040	779	7833	6258	8594	5484	123.2	98.9
C_Date Morrow Mtn point	7301	1000	8302	6300	9301	5301	7480	753	8221	6699	9001	5993	111.5	98.8
C_Date Early Archaic point	10201	1300	11502	8900	12801	7601	10199	1300	11543	8844	12784	7620		97.1
C_Date Pt Anomaly	12786	50	12837	12734	12886	12686	12782	104	12861	12730	12977	12557	99.4	99
C_Date Clovis point	13051	200	13252	12850	13451	12651	12810	128	12881	12726	13136	12558	81.6	98
Boundary							12810	128	12881	12726	13136	12558		98
P_Sequence Flamingo Bay														
U(0,3)	1.52	0.87	0.00	3.00	0.00	3.00	1.38	0.80	0.02	2.12	0.00	2.69	100	99.5
Exp(1,-10,0.5)	-0.55	1.00	-0.66	0.45	-2.69	0.45	-0.53	0.97						100
Outlier_Model General							-44	160	-49	28	-417	181		100

Supplementary Information Table 7. Prompt gamma-ray activation analysis (PGGA) elemental data in part per million (ppm) for select samples from Newtonville microstrat block.

Sample #	Layer	Depth (cm)	Boron (B)	Chlorine (Cl)	Vanadium (V)	Chromium (Cr)	Cobalt (Co)	Cadmium (Cd)	Neodymium (Nd)	Samarium (Sm)	Gadolinium (Gd)	Sulphur (S)	Calcium (Ca)	Aluminum (Al)	Silicon (Si)	Phosphorous (P)	Potassium (K)	Manganese (Mn)
2702	Mic-Strat-1	0-2	197	30	250	500	210	0	34	5	6	0	0	4600	14000	0	0	2700
2703	Mic-Strat-3	4-6	1580	600	1300	0	0	140	2800	100	2	0	0	23000	88000	110000	0	10200
2800	Mic-Strat-6	10-12	2040	900	0	6000	3700	0	1000	59	110	11000	30000	46000	150000	0	0	12000
2704	Mic-Strat-8	14-16	1086	400	800	0	0	0	240	27	34	0	0	27000	70000	10	0	10900
2705	Mic-Strat-9	16-18	1159	440	1300	1200	240	70	160	17	17	0	0	32000	77000	0	1000	11000

Parsons Island Bulk Sedimentary Organic Matter Geochemistry

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of SOM in the uppermost and lowermost Parsons Island samples are consistent with material derived primarily from C_3 photosynthetic plants ($\delta^{13}\text{C} \sim -25\%$) with elevated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values in between (10-45 cmbs) indicative of a mixed C_3 and C_4 organic matter input^{19,20} (Supplementary Information Table 7 and Supplementary Information Fig. 27). In the Ap Horizon (above 30 cmbs), the elevated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values could be indicative of past cultivation of C_4 crops (maize) or rapid mineralization of organic carbon related to agricultural practices (e.g., tilling). The significant and steady rise in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values above 30 cmbs supports the interpretation of accelerated organic matter decomposition linked to agricultural activities and the effects on nitrogen cycling in the Ap soil horizon²¹ with increased $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of SOM resulting from accelerated N loss with more rapid decomposition associated with agricultural and tilling practices. Additionally, any additions of N fertilizers will typically increase bulk sedimentary $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values due to ammonia volatilization. The very low C/N ratios of samples in the Ap horizon also support this interpretation as they indicate anomalously high nitrogen influx and potentially high carbon mineralization rates, resulting in C/N ratios well below 10. Most terrestrial vascular plants produce organic matter with C/N ratios well above 20²². The inferred YDB horizon at Parsons Island is characterized by a small decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and relatively steady $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values but a rapid increase in the C/N ratio of SOM. This rapid rise in C/N ratios may indicate a sudden increase in terrestrial vascular plant-derived SOM deposition, supported by the small concurrent decrease in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, or potentially an increase in recalcitrant black carbon (graphite) deposition. However, black carbon content was not analyzed in this study. The observed changes are very small and may simply indicate a slight change in deposition dynamics at the site or, more likely, a change in sea level leading to more terrestrial biomass near the exposure.

Methods: Instrumentation and Analytical Details for Shock-fractured Quartz

Candidate grains were investigated using a robust series of analyses using a wide range of high-resolution instruments as follows and adapted from Hermes *et al.*²³. These included optical transmission microscopy (OPT), epi-illumination microscopy (EPI), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), focused ion beam milling (FIB), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), fast-Fourier transform (FFT), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), and cathodoluminescence (CL).

Thin-sectioned slides. Selected sedimentary grains were wet-sieved to concentrate those between diameters of ~ 150 (#100 ASTM sieve) to ~ 850 μm (#20 ASTM sieve). Then, the sorted grains were treated with HCl to destroy carbonates. Grains were embedded in blue epoxy for better visibility, covering the entire 27 x 46 mm slide, and were sectioned at Spectrum Petrographics, Vancouver, WA. Sectioned slides were given a high-polish, microprobe-grade finish necessary for EBSD analyses. No cover slide was used.

HF Etching. Following Bunch *et al.*²⁴, Spectrum Petrographics, Vancouver, WA, etched thin-sectioned slides by exposure to 50% HF vapor for 2 min to dissolve amorphous quartz and make any lamellae more visible. Note that exposure for < 2 min was insufficient for etching and exposing shock fractures; exposure for > 2 min can damage the slides. After treatment with HF vapor, we performed another dH_2O rinse.

Alternately, we treated some slides with liquid HF for 2 min, after which we performed a dH_2O rinse, neutralized them with 5% sodium carbonate solution, rinsed them with dH_2O again, and then treated them with 5% HCl to remove carbonates. The HF vapor produced more consistent results than the liquid HF.

Multiple studies²⁵⁻³⁰ have demonstrated the utility of etching quartz grains with HF to differentiate between glass-filled shock features and glass-free tectonic deformation lamellae. Our study observed that HF sometimes lightly etches tectonic deformation lamellae to reveal broad, shallow depressions, as others reported^{27,29}. However, unlike shock fractures, these depressions in the damaged lattice did not extend more than a few microns into the grain and were not observed to contain amorphous silica.

Optical Transmission Microscopy (OPT). We made polished thin sections of quartz grains and meltglass to search for potentially shock-fractured quartz grains. Grains were examined using a petrographic polarizing microscope with a rotary stage. The microscope was equipped with transmitted light and epi-illumination (reflected light). First, epi-illumination and transmitted light were used with objective lenses ranging from 04x to 100x magnification. Once a candidate grain was identified as having potentially glass-filled shock fractures, it was rotated to extinction under cross polars. Photomicrographs were acquired under both transmitted light and epi-illumination.

Epi-Illumination Microscopy (EPI). This optical technique uses reflected light to image the surfaces of the grains investigated. It is useful in identifying fractures filled with glass because glass typically etches very well with HF.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Standard practices were used for SEM analyses. At the University of Oregon, we used a ThermoFisher Apreo 2 SEM with a CL detector. At Elizabeth City State University, North Carolina, SEM images were acquired in low-vacuum mode using a JEOL-6000 SEM system.

Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). SEM- and TEM-based EDS exposes a specimen to an electron beam that generates X-rays that vary according to the elements present in the sample. Standard practices were used for TEM analyses.

Using SEM-EDS, we manually selected for detection of the major elements with uncertainties of approximately $\pm 10\%$. At the University of Utah, secondary and backscattered electron images were collected using a Teneo SEM system (Thermofisher FEI, Hillsboro, OR).

Focused Ion Beam Milling (FIB). This technique prepares a thin specimen (avg: ~ 175 nanometers (nm) thick) by milling a quartz grain with focused gallium (Ga) ions. The resulting specimen, called a foil, is then analyzed using TEM.

At the CAMCOR facility of the University of Oregon, TEM samples of quartz foils were prepared using a Helios Dual Beam SEM FIB. At the Surface Analysis Laboratory at the University of Utah, TEM sample preparation of quartz foils from bulk specimens was performed on an FEI/Thermo Helios Nanolab 650. The lift-out procedure followed standard sample preparation techniques. First, an electron beam deposited a platinum layer locally. Next, an ion beam was used to deposit an additional platinum layer. Trenches were milled on each side of the protective layer. Cuts were then made to the underside, and a micromanipulator probe was placed in contact with the surface (Omniprobe 200). The probe was attached by depositing platinum, and the sample was cut free from the bulk. The lift-out was attached to a copper support grid using the micromanipulator probe. The sample was then thinned using the ion beam at progressively decreasing accelerating voltages, 30kV, 16kV, 8kV, and 2kV.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). TEM images were also acquired on the FIB foils. Standard practices were used for TEM analyses.

Selected Area Diffraction (SAD). When an electron beam passes through a thin FIB foil of quartz, the electron beam's interaction with the quartz atoms creates an electron diffraction pattern. SAD can reveal details of the grain's lattice parameters and crystalline orientation or the lack of structure in amorphous silica.

Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (STEM). Bright-field STEM images were acquired on focused ion beam foils. Standard practices were used for STEM analyses.

At the CAMCOR facility at the University of Oregon, Transmission/Scanning transmission electron microscopy, or (S)TEM, was performed on an FEI 80-300 Titan scanning/transmission electron microscope (STEM) equipped with an image corrector, High-Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF) detector, Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) detector, Gatan Imaging Filter (GIF), and a 4-megapixel Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) camera. Microscope magnification was calibrated using a standard cross-grating carbon replica (2,160 lines/mm) evaporated with Au-Pd (Ted Pella #607). All images, diffraction patterns, and EDX maps were collected at 300kV and processed using Digital Micrograph, version 3.32.2403.0. Because electron microscopy is capable of causing irradiation-induced amorphization³¹, quartz grains were examined at low magnification using low voltages and very short image-acquisition times. We confirmed that we were not creating amorphous quartz by viewing the nearby crystalline lattice.

At the University of Utah, STEM/TEM was performed on a JEOL 2800 operated at 200 kV. EDS data was collected and processed using ThermoFisher Noran System 7 software. Spectral maps were processed as net counts (background subtracted) using a 5x5 kernel size. Quantitative results were obtained using the Cliff-Lorimer method with absorption correction.

Fast-Fourier Transform (FFT) and Inverse Fast-Fourier Transform (IFFT). The diffraction characteristics of the FIB foils were investigated using FFT, an image processing technique for analyzing high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images in reciprocal space. The FFT algorithm calculates the frequency distribution of pixel intensities in an HRTEM image and then displays any periodicity as spots in an output image, thus revealing the crystal's structure. HRTEM and FFT allow the measurement of interatomic spacings, known as d-spacings, measured

in nm or angstroms (Å). *IFFT imagery* is derived from spot diffraction patterns in an FFT image and is used to show the areas of the crystalline structure that contribute to the diffraction spots shown in an FFT image.

Cathodoluminescence (SEM-CL). Luminescence occurs in the SEM when high-energy electrons bombard some materials. After that, photons are emitted at characteristic wavelengths, and those emissions are recorded in panchromatic (185–850 nm wavelengths) and 3-filtered (RGB) formats. Red, green, and blue channels were optimized individually to obtain the maximum information from the image. Thus, the color information in the images is non-quantitative. They were composited to create a 24-bit color image.

At the University of Oregon, we used a ThermoFisher Apreo 2 SEM with a CL detector. The cathodoluminescent (CL) images were synchronously captured at red (R), green (G), and blue (B) wavelengths on coated thin sections in low-vacuum mode on a Thermo Apreo2 S FE-SEM at 10kV using 3.2nA of beam current at ~10 mm working distance with 50Pa of chamber pressure to balance charge. Wavelength ranges were red: 595-813 nm, green: 495-615, and blue: 291-509 nm. Backscatter (BSE) and secondary (SE) electron images were captured with similar beam settings.

Micro-Raman. We investigated the shock fractures using micro-Raman. The objective magnification is 100X, and the laser power is 20 mW at 780 nm with an integration time of 5s. By mounting the thin-sectioned slide on a motorized stage and collecting Raman spectra at specified intervals, it is possible to analyze the spectra and determine whether areas contain crystalline quartz and amorphous silica.

Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD). This is an SEM-based analytical technique in which an electron beam scans across a crystalline sample tilted at 70°. The diffracted electrons produce what are called Kikuchi patterns that reveal the microstructural properties of the sample. EBSD was also used to determine the quartz grains' crystallographic orientations. We often used an EBSD technique called "PRIAS," an acronym for "Pattern Region of Interest Analysis System."

At the University of Utah, secondary and backscattered electron SEM images were collected using a Teneo system (Thermofisher FEI; Hillsboro, OR). EDS, EBSD, and CL analyses were similarly conducted with the same SEM system installed with the following detectors: an Octane Elite EDS system (EDAX, Pleasanton, CA) was used to collect elemental spectra; a Monarc CL Detector (Gatan; Pleasanton, CA) was used for cathodoluminescence studies. SEM beam energy and current were optimized to meet the requirements of each analysis mode. Before imaging, sample slides were polished to 0.20 µm roughness with colloidal silica suspension and washed with water to remove residues. The slides were then coated with 5-nm-thick carbon using a Leica EM ACE600 coater (Leica Microsystems, Inc., Deerfield, IL) to prevent charging during the imaging process.

Here are the EBSD analytical techniques used in Fig. 19:

Panel a: "Grain reference orientation deviation." Each point is shaded according to its angular deviation to a reference orientation for the grain to which it belongs.

Panel a: "PRIAS." An acronym for a Pattern Region of Interest Analysis System. This technique has also been termed a virtual forward scatter detector (or VFSD) or a synthetic backscatter detector, among other names. The idea is that each pixel in an EBSD pattern can essentially be used as a forward scatter detector.

Panel b: "Inverse pole Fig.." This panel shows the position of a sample direction relative to the crystal reference frame.

Panel b: "Image quality." Each point in the scan is shaded according to its relative quality.

Panel c: "Local orientation spread." The point at the center of a grain kernel is shaded according to the average misorientation all points in the kernel make with all other points in the kernel - that is, the orientation spread within the kernel.

Panel c: "Image quality." See above.

Panel d: "Inverse pole Fig.." See above.

Panel d: "Image quality." See above.

Panel e: "Grain reference orientation deviation." See above.

Panel e: "PRIAS." See above.

Panel f: "Inverse pole Fig.." See above.

Panel f: "PRIAS." See above.

Universal stage. We also investigated the shock fractures using the universal stage. However, we could not determine Miller indices because the observed shock fractures are non-planar and not oriented along the quartz crystals' crystallographic planes; thus, they cannot be accurately measured and compared to planar features.

Image processing. Most images were globally adjusted for balance, brightness, contrast, and sharpness, and some images were cropped to fit the space. A few images were rotated for clarity, and the legends and scale bars were repositioned at the bottom of the Figure. Legends sometimes became unreadable for the RGB and resized images, so

they were replaced with the original legend. EDS Figures were composited from multiple channels. No data within the figures were changed or obscured when making any adjustments.

Parsons Island Bulk Sedimentary Organic Matter Geochemistry Methods. We analyzed the stable carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) isotope composition and organic carbon and nitrogen content of sedimentary organic matter (SOM) in the Parson's Island samples using a Costech 4010 elemental analyzer interfaced with a Thermo Delta V Plus stable isotope mass spectrometer at the University of North Carolina Wilmington. We loaded the dried and homogenized sediment samples into tin capsules for analysis. Carbon and nitrogen isotopic data are reported in the delta (δ) per mille (‰) notation that relates to the Vienna-Pee Dee belemnite (VPDB) and atmospheric nitrogen (AIR) standards, respectively, using the following equation:

$$\delta X = 1000 * \left[\left(\frac{R_{\text{sample}}}{R_{\text{standard}}} \right) - 1 \right] \quad (1)$$

Where $X = ^{13}\text{C}$ or ^{15}N ; and $R = ^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ or $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$, respectively. Standard deviations of replicate measurements of USGS 40 and USGS 41a glutamic acid standards during analyses were +/- 0.3‰.

Bayesian Coding

These Bayesian analyses were typically allowed to run for a maximum of 1-2 million iterations. Thus, attempts to replicate these analyses for a different number of iterations may produce differences, but they are typically insignificant.

Bayesian coding for Newtonville

```
Options()
{
  Resolution=5;
  Curve="IntCal20";
  BCAD=FALSE;
  kIterations=100;
};
Plot()
{
  Outlier_Model("General",Exp(1,-10,0.5),U(0,3),"t");
  P_Sequence("Newtonville, generalized",0.3,2)
  {
    Boundary();
    C_Date("UIC 1295",calBP(2005-16800),1700){z=38.0;Outlier("General",1);};
    C_Date("Pt Anomaly",calBP(1950-12785),50){z=12.0;Outlier("General",1);};
    R_Date("D-AMS 043966",10858,34){z=12.0;Outlier("General",1);};
    R_Date("UCI-250410",10185,25){z=12.0;Outlier("General",1);};
      R_Date("UGA-65780",960,20){z=12.0;Outlier();};
      R_Date("UGA-65781",960,20){z=12.0;Outlier();};

  }

  Boundary();
};
};
```

Bayesian coding for Parsons Island

```
Options()
{
  UseF14C=FALSE;
  kIterations=100;
};
Plot()
{
  Outlier_Model("General",Exp(1,-10,10),U(0,4),"t");
  P_Sequence("Parsons Island",0.05,1)
  {
```

```

Boundary();

C_Date("UW3804",2021-24600,2400){z=180;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("UW3803",2021-24200,1640){z=160;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("UW3802",2021-21200,1780){z=130;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("UW3801",2021-19300,1560){z=100;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("UW3800",2021-17400,2270){z=65;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("Pt anomaly",1950-12785,50){z=47.5;Outlier("General",1)};
R_Date("D-AMS 043965",10753,37){z=42.5;Outlier("General",1)};

```

```

Boundary("");
};
};

```

Bayesian coding for Flamingo Bay

```

Options()
{
Resolution=5;
Curve="IntCal20";
BCAD=FALSE;
kIterations=100;
};
Plot()
{
Outlier_Model("General",Exp(1,-10,0.5),U(0,3),"t");
P_Sequence("Flamingo Bay",0.3,2)
{
Boundary();
C_Date("Clovis point",calBP(1950-13050),200){z=54.25;Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};
C_Date("Pt Anomaly",calBP(1950-12785),50){z=54.25; Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("Early Archaic point",calBP(1950-10200),1300){z=54.25;Outlier();color="orange"};
C_Date("Morrow Mtn point",calBP(1950-7300),1000){z=36.0; Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};
C_Date("Middle Archaic point",calBP(1950-7400),1500){z=34.0; Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};
C_Date("Savannah River point",calBP(1950-4275),575){z=22.5; Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};
C_Date("Woodland point",calBP(1950-1175),325){z=12.50; Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};
Boundary();
};
};

```

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